
smFISH: preparation of mouse lung tissue for processing with smFISH

Short name: smFISH-lung-tissue-preparation

Version: 2

Date: 1.3.2025

Abstract: Protocol describing the preparation of lung tissue for staining with smFISH. Protocol developed by Sandra Curras Alonso and Charles Fouillad (Institut Curie) and used in (Curras-Alonso *et al.*, 2023).

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1 Materials

1.1 Reagents and materials

1X PBS	Invitrogen, AM9624
Sucrose	Sigma, S7903
PFA (paraformaldehyde)	Euromedex, 15714-S
OCT (optimal cutting temperature compound)	VWR, 411243
APTS (3-aminopropyl triethoxysilane)	Sigma, A3648-100ML

Embedding molds	VWR, POLS18646ACODE45
Coverslips	Menzel-Glaser, 20x20, #1

1.2 Equipment

Cryostat	Leica CM 1950
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2 Methods

2.1 Tissue extraction and embedding

1. Mice were injected with a mixture of **100 mg/kg ketamine and 10 mg/kg xylazine**, and we waited for them to fall asleep entirely.
2. The ribcage was opened, the heart was perfused with 10 mL of cold 1XPBS pH 7.4, and the heart was resected just after the perfusion was finished.
3. The mouse trachea was perfused with cold 4% **PFA** until the lungs were fully expanded with no air left.
4. The trachea was closed with a thread to avoid PFA leakage.
5. The lungs were resected from the rib cage and kept in a Falcon tube with cold 4% PFA overnight (O/N) under rotation at 4°C.
6. After fixation, the five lobes were separated and individually kept in cold 1x PBS containing 30% sucrose for 6 hours under rotation at 4°C.
7. Lobes were rinsed in cold 1x PBS and pre-embedded in cold 50% **OCT** diluted in 1x PBS for 30 min under rotation at 4°C.
8. Finally, each lobe was embedded in **square embedding molds** containing OCT, then frozen in dry ice for 20 minutes, and stored at -80°C.
9. **🔔 LONG-TERM STORAGE at -80°C possible.**

2.2 Tissue cutting for smFISH

1. Coverslips are cleaned as described in the smFISH base protocol.
2. Coverslips are coated **with silane** for better tissue attachment
 - a. Dry coverslips in an oven at 70°C for 10 min.
 - b. Coverslips were coated with **2% APTS in H₂O** for 2 minutes.
 - c. Rinse 2X with water.
 - d. The coating is activated in the oven at 70°C for 60 min.
3. In a cryostat, OCT-embedded mouse lung lobes were cut into 16 µm tissue sections and mounted on cleaned and coated coverslips.
4. Coverslips with lung tissue sections were placed into 6-well plates.
 - a. Fixed with cold 4% PFA for 15 min at 4°C.

- b. Washed twice with cold 1x PBS.
 - c. Kept in 70% ethanol at 4°C O/N.
5. **STORAGE for up to 2 months at -20°C.**

3 References

Curras-Alonso, S. *et al.* (2023) 'An interactive murine single-cell atlas of the lung responses to radiation injury', *Nature Communications*, 14(1), p. 2445. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-38134-z>.

4 Version history

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1	11.10.2024	Mueller F	Initial version, based on (Curras-Alonso <i>et al.</i> , 2023)
v2	1.3.2025	Mueller F	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.